

CONSUMER FOOD-CHOICE BEHAVIOUR MODEL

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ABSTRACT

International festivals are common in all countries. However countries hosting international festivals are unaware of the expectations and behavior of travellers related to their food choice behaviour before their visit. A study was conducted with specific reference to Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF), Sarawak, Malaysia, to explore the food choice behaviour of international travellers relating to neophobic behaviour. The study followed interpretive research philosophy and exploratory study design with phenomenological interpretations, case studies and Delphi method. The research design integrated a longitudinal design during 2016 to 2017 period to develop a food choice consumer behaviour model with triangulated tools and methods, identified causative factors related to consumer food choices. The study followed purposive sampling with a sample of 148 travellers during the festival and data collection was done with the triangulated tools of in-depth interviews, content analysis and observation following phenomenology method. The investigators came up with a thematic model in relation to food choice behaviour of RWMF travellers, by extending theoretical and practical contributions.

Keywords: *Food choice, consumer attitude, social support, self-efficacy, neophobic, intention to revisit, social media, theory of planned behavior.*

INTRODUCTION

Food and food choices are closely related to concepts in deciding travel destinations. Food choice behaviour is a predictor for food consumption patterns, which in turn are closely associated with the outcome of food choice behaviour – the destination image. Availability of ‘familiar foods’ are one of the factors that decides traveller’s intention to visit tourist destinations providing solutions to neophobic behaviour. Though several aspects of consumer behaviour and consumer decision-making were examined in diverse studies (Chen & Chen, 2010; Al-Tarawneh, 2012; Schiffman, O’Cass, Paladino & Carlson, 2014), its association with music festivals and neophobic attitude of visitors has seldom deliberated in tourism studies. When visitors of music festival look at a destination, they not only look at

the 'music' alone but also the availability of 'safe and variety food choices' that will be interpreted as a 'rare experience' during their stay in a destination. To examine the visitor's intention to revisit, especially in relation to neophobic attitude, a study was conducted among the international travellers of Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF). To arrive at the conceptual framework, the study followed the 'lived experiences' of travellers with heuristic phenomenological interpretations and case studies. The study developed a theme with the support of qualitative interpretations, confirming the observations with Delphi techniques. External validity of the observations has arrived at through triangulated methods and tools with expert confirmations (Delphi Technique). The observations of the study can be used in establishing the relationship between neophobic attitude of visitors and their intention to choose destinations as well as extending practical significance to the RWMF coordinators.

Research Question – Qualitative

1. Which are the categories closely related to the neophobic food choice attitude of travellers visiting Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF)?

Research Objective – Qualitative Research

1. To identify the Food Choice attitudinal categories of international travellers visiting RWMF.
2. To understand the factors associated with international traveller's intention to revisit Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF).

RESEARCH METHOD

The first phase of this research followed a qualitative methodology with triangulated method of data collection. With the some unstructured and structured questions, the investigators tried to explore the relevant categories through coding. In first phase the investigator expected to obtain the food choice attitudinal categories and allied variables and come up with a thematic model. The triangulation (tools and methods) in this research consists of:

- Gathering of all documents related to neophobic behaviour of travellers of RWMF;
- Conducting 112 interviews with travellers;
- Conducting interviews with school Professors/lecturers of tourism;
- Conducting interviews with tour agents and tour operators and seeking their completion of questionnaires and;
- Following case studies and phenomenology with narration as triangulated methods of research.

The objective of first phase was there by to identify the categories linked to the factor 'food choice attitude of neophobic travellers' of RWMF and come up with a thematic model, for examining its possible measurement through quantitative research. Research hypotheses were constructed at the conclusion of Phase 1.

Triangulation

In order to improve the authenticity of the observations made in the research, the investigators usually apply triangulate process, which supports answering the research questions with more validity (Kumar, 2014). Triangulated approach supports the researchers to fill the pitfalls and lacunas of other research approaches as well as enhances the credibility and transferability of knowledge obtains from the field (Kumar, 2014). Triangulation at the methodological level is highly implemented by many researchers in order to ascertain the exactness and the definiteness (Mitchell, 1986). The methodological triangulation is integrated with the research design of the study (Bums & Grove, 1993). This particular study followed phenomenology, case studies and Delphi Technique as the triangulation methods that to identify the food choice categories and arriving at thematic model.

Phenomenology

A study, which explores the rich feelings and emotions of human being and share the way in which things are perceived - how these appear in our consciousness is termed as Phenomenology (Langdrige, 2007). With this approach, the researchers tries to clarify states and conditions experienced by people in everyday life, lasting as realistic as possible to the phenomenon and to the context in which it appears in the world (Giorgi & Giorgi, 2003a, p.109). In this research the investigators looked at the feelings and emotions associated with the food choices behaviour of international travellers visiting the Rainforest World Music Festival in relation to neophobic attitude and travellers intention to revisit the festival in Sarawak, Malaysia.

Case Study

This particular study followed heuristic phenomenology integrating case study research design as research strategy to identify the factors related to traveller's neophobic. Case interviews are often used as part of the initial assessment and arriving at explicit and implicit categories and variables based on the topic under study. Some of the case study content supported the researcher to get some insight into food choices attitude of international travellers visiting the Rainforest World Music Festival in relation to neophobic and their decision to revisit. Thus, the researchers include short interviews with the international travellers visiting during Rainforest World Music Festival. This was done during their arrival in airport, as well as days before the festival and started.

FINDINGS

Interviews with Respondents

Informant 1

“I have heard about Rainforest Festival. However, I came to know that this festival is somewhere deep in one of eastern state of Malaysia. Though I love music, and usually participate in music festivals, I don’t have the courage to come down to attend this Rainforest Music Festival due to lack of food safety. My husband but encouraged me to travel down to Sarawak, for one week stay, taking the risk, though we were uncertain about the food choices. There is no food authenticity and we were very much unfamiliar about the food choices in the Rainforest World Music Festival”.

Informant 2

“I read the information about Rainforest World Music Festival from website as well as blogs. Found interesting. Some e-forums also there in the internet to get familiarize with the event. Nevertheless, I got only little idea about the food variety for the visitors of the rain forest festivals, over websites or internet. A friend of mine then told me that there will be plenty of food choices for the visitors, especially ethnic cuisines in the Rainforest World Music Festival. Though I do aware from traveller’s blogs that that they have suffered food allergy with the intake of local food available during the event. I will rethink whether to come next year to this event or not, since my food choices are not well catered during my stay”.

Informant 3

“I love the voice of Sona Jobarteh (Gambia, Africa). She plays the Kora, an African harp. She was my favourite performer. I just wanna listen to her voice and the strings. I came to know that she would be visiting Rainforest festival. However, being a lonely traveller, I feared of going Rainforest Festival to listen her songs, due to unknown place as well as unreliable food choices. I really cared about the food hygiene and the way restaurants service. I had a very bad stomach pain due to food poison, in one of the festive occasion in another country”.

Informant 4

“I am from Philippines. During my last year Rainforest World Music Festival trip, I did not get any Filipino food. Philippine food was not available at all. It was learned from the blogs that all kind of food available to accommodate people from all region. At the end of the day, my days moved with local food alone. The restaurants are not at all clean. The food quality is not reliable at all. I had indigestion health issues for a week. I had to go near by clinic to get medication. Though the program was good, I feel dissatisfied with the available food choices for visitors during Rainforest Festival. No more, I want to visit this festival”.

Informant 5

“I am a continuous visitor of this Rainforest World Music Festival for the past four years. I am finding that this festival is so organized and providing better satisfaction to me to be aware of the indigenous music. On my first visit, here in 2014 I had lot of apprehension with regard to the food choices since the information related to varied food choices are not available either in the website or when I consulted into with friends. I would second their opinion that the food choices are limited and the quality of food available was unreliable. I am uncomfortable with the local food options. I feel that the organizers should consider the traveller’s some preferences rather pushing the local food to be experienced. More people will come if they organize the event with food variety and exhibit those through all Social Medias”.

Delphi Technique Application

In order to identify the categories connected to the factor ‘food choice behaviour’, this research followed Delphi Technique. The study was conducted among the international travellers visited in Rainforest World Music Festival in the Santubong area in Kuching, Sarawak, Malaysia, linking food choice behaviour and intention to revisit. As it is evidenced this particular approach is used as an effective method with the support of experts from gastronomy research field and stakeholders of festive tourism, in order to set the objectives to commence an inquiry into the policy or to extend actual prediction of the occurrence of future events (Kumar, 2014). The study strictly followed Delphi Technique requirements. Appropriate identification and selection of experts was done to explore the factors related to food choice behaviour and traveller’s decision to revisit the festive event. The investigators identified 26 experts from travel and tourism industry as Delphi Team, who had already participated in this event as well as international acclaimed specialists. The study ensured the gender neutrality by incorporating experts from male (12 male members, 60%) and female groups (8 female members, 40%). As it is mentioned above these experts are highly conversant with the traveller’s neophobic behaviour as well as gastronomic attitude during their travel to tourist and festive destinations.

Round 1

Usually the round one of the Delphi process starts with the explorative open ended questions. This supports the investigator to get better grip on the concepts undertaken for the study as well as supplying specific information about a content area from the experts gathered (Custer, Scarcella & Stewart, 1999).

Research Questions

1. Which are the factors closely related to food choice behaviour of Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF) travellers?

Round 2

Soon after the completion of the first round, the investigators have initiated the second round with the screening of 68 categories which have a high and low effect on food choices identified with corresponding items. The process further reduced to 28 categories, which have high and low propinquity on food choices behaviour, well acknowledged. Organization of the items in 28 categories under one factor was done with appropriate loaded items.

Round 3

During third level, evaluation of the 28 categories under one factor, have items with high and moderately-high closeness on food choices attitude identified. During this evaluation process the expert opinion on the appropriateness of the core factors well acknowledged. Finally in this round, 13 categories of food choice factor finalized under one factor.

Observations Based on Confirmation

Based on the Delphi Technique, the researchers have identified prominent food choice attitudinal categories closely knit with the neophobic traveller's intention to revisit the Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF). The study reports with Food Authenticity (90%), Food Familiarity (85%), Food Variety (90%), Food Safety (95%), Food Hygiene (90%), Food Availability (85%), Food Reliability (90%), Food Taste (90%), Food Allergy (85%), Food Service (80%), Food Service Establishments (80%), Food Poison (90%), Food Ingredients (90%) are the major categories in neophobic food choices, identified by the experts in relation to attending Rain Rainforest World Music Festival (RWMF). The food choice factors confirmed by the experts are indicated in the table below.

Table 1: Delphi Application on Precarious Working Condition

Factor	Categories	No of Items	No of experts	% of Expert Consensus
EXPERIENTIAL FOOD-CHOICE ATTITUDE	Food Authenticity	4	18	90
	Food Familiarity	5	17	85
	Food Variety	5	18	90
	Food Safety	3	19	95
	Food Hygiene	4	18	90
	Food Availability	5	17	85
	Food Reliability	2	18	90
	Food Taste	4	18	90
	Food Allergy	3	17	85
	Food Service	3	16	80
	Establishments	4	16	80
	Food Poison	4	17	85
	Food Ingredients	4	18	85

Thematic Model Development

The study has come out with following themes in relation to traveller's food choice and intention revisit.

Figure 1: Thematic Model

Content Analysis

Food as a Destination of Choice

Several studies have come out in explaining the food choice behaviour. The core function of tourism industry has to make provision of best of food to the travellers as well as leaving best of food experiences during their visit in travel destinations (Murphy et al., 2000; Karim & Chi, 2010). The cuisines of the tourist destinations are leaving several memorable experiences to the visitors and it has accounted a considerable element of both local and international tourism expenditure (Du Rand, Heath & Alberts, 2003; McKercher, Okumus & Okumus B., 2008; Nield, Kozak & LeGrys, 2000; Sparks, Bowen & Klag, 2004). Chaney and Ryan (2012) rightly pointed out in this context that a common tourist spends about one third of their travel costs on food-related purchases. The gastronomy experience as investigated in this research was with specific reference to festive events rather from a broader perspective. Especially on festivals the travellers do only have the option to eat out at food precincts or hawker centres in the surrounding area or which are extended by the event organizers. Such unique experiences had a critical role in their association and attachment with the destination, whether favourable or unfavourable (Pendergast, 2006).

Add to this argument, Karim and Chi (2010) also indicates that food-related experiences can enrich the overall destination experience and involvement.

Neophobic Attitude

Neophobic is intensely related with the fear or a kind of dislike arising from anything new or unfamiliar thing, which are closely knit with both physical and emotional states of a human being. It is defined as unwillingness toward and/or an avoidance of new food (Pliner & Hobden, 1992, p. 105). Birch (1999, p. 49) defined food neophobic as a human behaviour where they tried to avoid novel foods. While some authors (Pliner & Hobden, 1992, p. 107) defined it as a personality trait in terms of their decision to proximity avoids new foods People have less neophobic characteristics will show the willingness to try both familiar and unfamiliar food. While the other show the reluctance to take up (Tuorila, Lahteenemaki, Pohjalainen & Lotti, 2001). The familiarity and unfamiliarity of foods have the influence on traveller's decision to visit certain locations or attend certain festive event. This indicates that the traveller's likes and dislikes towards the available foods depends on their familiarity and unfamiliarity of foods items available. Hence it is necessary to realize that the food choice behaviour of the travellers needs to be examined with regard to its association with the intention to visit Rain Forest World Festival (McIntosh, 1996).

Social Support

The norms of the society especially the group perception towards certain aspects generate favourable and unfavourable attitude among individuals. This will be true among the traveller's food choices during their intent to visit since their attitude will be influenced by several reference groups (Ajzen, 1991). Now days, with the exposure to social media, traveller's friends, family or social groups are well aware of the varied food availability in travel destinations (McKnight, 2007). These social groups thus create pressure among the travellers intention to consume particular foods and for trying new foods (Schucker, 1987; Alar, 1990).

Self-Efficacy

In addition to the attitude and normative belief, one of the major factor influence human attitude is perceived behavioural control. Whether the 'perception of control' matches with the 'actual control' that decides human intention to engage in certain behaviour (Armitage & Conner, 2001). Such behaviour control is further divided into perceived self-efficacy and perceived controllability (Ajzen, 2002). To what extend the travellers are aware about the varied food choice available in the event that provide better confidence among them to revisit Availability of information from varied sources like social networking sites, the website of the event and related blogs etc., will make them better aware about the food choices and will lead them to take the decision on whether to visit or revisit the event, contextually Rainforest World Music Festival.

Social Media and Behavioural Performance

With the advent of internet of things and social media applications travellers are well aware of the food and nutrition. Connectivity facilitated by the social media has the capability to influence the food choices of travellers. *E-marketing* that involves producing and distribution of food availability and food content on *social media networks*, for example blogs, microblogs (e.g., Twitter), online communities (e.g., Facebook and TripAdvisor), media sharing sites (e.g., Flickr and YouTube), social bookmarking sites (e.g., Delicious), social knowledge sharing sites (e.g., Wikitravel), and other tools serves with an objective of greater awareness goals. The knowledge of food choices during festive occasions and tourist places are more or less available in electronic *media* and it seems to be growing due to technology advancement. These changes have some or the other way influence the *traveller's neophobic behaviour* in their search for genuine, authentic and familiar foods available. As it is reported personal use of social media is one of the best predictors for behavioural performance (Armitage & Conner, 2001; Rise, et al., 2010). Contextualizing the discussion to Rain Forest Music Festival, the organizers are making use of several social media channels for the dissemination of information. These observations deduce from the context of social media reports that intentions to use social networking sites predicted search for right food in relation to their travel decision (Pelling & White, 2009).

Visitor Satisfaction

Satisfaction of the travellers during their visit or stay develops lasting impressions of destinations even long after the visit ends (Hall & Mitchell, 2002; Hall, Sharples & Smith, 2003; Henderson, 2009). In addition to the travel itinerates these visits also provide intense personal experiences related to the food and food choices leaving better inner happiness and joy (Cooper & Hall, 2008; LaSalle & Britton, 2003). The visitor satisfaction is closely related to one's inner relations based on the expositional match. The experience a traveller derives during their visit leads to a favourable and unfavourable intention to make a revisit. Food availability based on the traveller's expectation thus acting as one the variable towards visitor satisfaction. This indicates that the experience they have about the past visits, remarks about the destinations from various sources in relation to variety of food choices, in correlation with their expectations will have high influence on their satisfaction and intention to make a revisit. This argument need to be cross validated in the context Rain Forest World Music Festival, which is an annual event organized in the Sarawak part of Malaysia, where many international travellers do visit.

Thematic Model Development (Intermediary Factors)

Figure 2: Research Framework with Theoretical Assertion

The study finally arrived at research frame with proper categories and variables to explain the influence of food choice behaviour in relation to theory of planned behaviour with the social media and visitor satisfaction as mediator to explain visitor's intention to revisit Rainforest World Music Festival.

Discussion

Food consumption is a subjective variable. Attitude towards food choices vary from individual traveller to another. This indicates that each traveller has food related personality traits. This food related personality trait which is closely linked to the neophobic personality has begun to be recognized as significant psychological factor affecting traveller's food consumption. A familiarity with the food develops a favourable attitude and unfamiliarity with the food develops an unfavourable attitude among the travellers during their visit in travel destinations (Pliner & Salvy, 2006). This situation is unchanging over time and reliable across situations.

Focused on human attitude, this qualitative research analysed the factors correlated to RWMF traveller's food choices behaviour and their intention to revisit. The objective of this exploratory research was to understand and identify the factors related to neophobic attitude of travellers. Food Authenticity, Food Familiarity, Food Variety, Food Safety, Food Hygiene, Food Availability, Food Reliability, Food Taste, Food Allergy, Food Service, Food

Service Establishments, Food Poison, Food Ingredients are the major categories in association with travellers food choices.

The first and second category identified by the expert in this research is food authenticity and food familiarity. It is reported by many researchers that there are several health crises of the past decade (BSE in 1996 and 2000, foot-and-mouth disease in 2001, avian flu in 2005, cucumber crisis in 2011), patterns of fraud relating to the authenticity of the food (Horsegate, 2013) and the ongoing debate concerning the safety of certain processes (e.g. accusation of GMOs in 2012) has developed increasing distrust of the consumers for the quality of food products. The tourists who will be travelling to several visitor destinations will look at all means to gather information on the availability of food choices whether it is familiar with their food choices and taste. Henceforth the food authenticity is an important aspect traveller's will be looking into for their better visitor experience. The traveller's intention to revisit thus may relate to their familiar food choice experience with visitor satisfaction. Contextualizing the concept to RWMF, better the food authenticity the organizers can extend to the traveller's better the confidence they have with them to revisit the festival.

Another food choice factor which influences tourist food consumption is variety-seeking. This indicates a personality trait where the travellers pursue variety in their choices of services and goods' (Kahn, 1995, p. 139). Foods are available in endless range and food choices are a main constituent of all purchase decisions made by consumers (Grunert, 1997). While some of the destinations leave better choice to the visitors by providing varied food availability, some of them totally deny it with local and ethnic food choices. It is rightly pointed out in this context that some travellers like a variety of foods while others might be picky eaters. There will be preferences or choices of one food product over another with due consideration to the familiarity and unfamiliarity attitude viz., the neophobic attitude. Like or dislike thus, reflects the assessment of quality of a product (Franchi, 2012) which is highly applicable to travellers when they visit different countries. Safety of selection of local and ethnic choices depends upon individual traveller's interest and taste. Nonetheless, it is reported by the respondents that any event which can accommodate better variety of food choices, more number of traveller's will prefer such tourist destination.

As we know, a travel which will accompany with eating and drinking. These two always go together. However on several occasion due to unhygienic food availability the travel may end up with several health illness like diarrhoea and easily getting sick. The travellers are usually extra careful with the food hygiene, before they take a decision to travel certain region where the hygiene and cleanliness in serving food. It is expected by every travellers that the food handlers should follow utmost food hygiene as well as the premises should ensure cleanliness. The food handlers should not make the food unhygienic by practicing low-level personal hygiene. Restaurant and service cleanliness is considered as one of the most significant conditions when customers evaluate overall restaurant quality or decide their levels of satisfaction. Following the right hygienic practices can enhance the confidence level of travellers visiting new places and encourage them to participate with satisfaction. It is rightly pointed out in this context that in a competitive service environment, managers (organizers of RWMF) should understand their customers (travellers) and provide service that increases their ability to attract new customers (travellers) and to win the loyalty of existing customers (travellers), as well as increasing the positive word-of-mouth effect (Boulding, Karla, Staelin and Zeithaml, 1993; Berkman, Lindquist & Sirgy, 1997; Cronin, Michael & Thomas, 2000; Walter, Edvardsson & Ostrom,

2010). Traveller's intention to visit is thus influenced by food hygiene, food service hygiene and food premise hygiene. Kivela and Crotts (2006) contend that motivation to travel for food/gastronomy is a valid construct, and that food plays an important role in affecting the overall tourist experience and intention to revisit a destination.

As it is envisaged, the social media with the support of emergent technologies have paved better probability for networking and knowledge sharing. The emergence of online social media challenges the existing marketing paradigms (Shao et al., 2012, p. 87). The travellers are very much interconnected through social media platform. *Food* is widely accepted as of great importance in tourists' experiences by researchers. Availability of information from social media platforms like Facebook, twitter, travel blogs etc. develop better understanding on the reliable food choices prior to their visit or before the decision-making. A better dissemination of information through social media platform supports the organizers for effective diffusion of marketing events.

As we aware, the E-marketing, comprises developing devices for purposefully determining discussions. E-marketing significantly to be adopted by festival organizers (RWMF), as future improvements, which is strongly dependent on social media. Hence, it is released that social media will be a platform of marketing, which will work more efficiently in comparison with traditional marketing approach in disseminating information on food variety, food choices and food reliability, leading to better intention to revisit.

Food Allergy (FA) is one of the visitor health evils in varied tourist destinations that can affect both adults and children (travellers). Food handlers in travel and tourism destinations hold the responsibility to prepare allergen-free food for the visitors from various part of the world. The allergic perceptions develop fears among the visitors and can have can give a negative impact especially in social and psychological effect on their intention to visit an unfamiliar locations. To ensure safe food choices to the visitors the organizers can take appropriate choices to avoid the risk factors of food allergy when preparing, making, cooking, storing and transporting the food products, especially for raw material, food is crucial to ensure that the food is not contaminated with food allergen. It is imperative to appoint a responsible staff member in facilitating all allergy/intolerance related requirements and who is qualified in the area. Proper training to all the vendors in the tourist destination on basic food allergen controls and safety food preparation practices can ensure better food choice confidence to the travellers. An allergy free food destinations can thus enhance the intention to revisit among the visitors, contextualizing to RWMF.

Even though food is important in destination choice, sufficient reassuring theories and investigational examination do not clarify the present phenomenon (food choice behaviour). Several studies have shown the significance of food as a determinant of attitudes toward the destination. It has been proved that food is one of the components of destination image (Quan & Wang, 2004). Intention to visit or revisit the same destination is a matter of choice to the affluent group like tourists.

It is argued in this context that local food holds the potential to enhance sustainability in tourism, whereby the tourism planners or the organizers of any event should work hand in hand to satisfy the traveller's choice of variety of food having different tastes; contribute to the authenticity and acceptability of the destination. Thus, availability of variety of foods with better tastes and flavour has considerable potential to enhance visitor experiences and to contribute to the branding and competitive marketing of RWMF

destination. It is, important to assure reliable and dependable cuisine of marketable local food as well as regional foods that need to be approached with a delicate balance.

Implications

Practical implications

Ensuring food authenticity and better familiarity of the food choices in the event of RWMF, has high practical implications on destination choice among visitors. Identifying the factors correlated to food choices provide better insight into travellers food selections. Visitors make use of varied platform for the collect of information related to food choices in an event. They will be gathering information about food authenticity, taste, ingredients, reliability, safety, allergic probability, food service cleanliness etc., to assure that they will be visiting a place which is away from health related illness and meeting their expected visitor experience during their stay. The importance of choice of participating an event destination can be seen as associated with the importance of mode which is closely food expected food availability. Hence is it is indisputably deliberated that food choice behaviour of travellers need to be well taken care of by the event organizers to get better flow of visitors during Rainforest World Music Festival. The organizers may make use of better social media platforms for the dissemination of information about the food choices to the travellers, from across the world, which enhance the visitor by ensuring visitor satisfaction.

The role of social media, also acting as a technology driven information-sharing platform, had the property to gather all the reference groups in one platform. Social media, widely adopted by visitors to collaboratively by search, organize, share, and annotate their travel stories and experiences through blogs, micro blogs, online communities, media sharing sites, social bookmarking sites, social knowledge sharing sites and other tools have high impact on voyager's awareness of preferred food choices and their intention to visit or revisit among the RWMF.

Theoretical Implications

The study explored the attitudinal factors related to food choices among the travellers without identifying proper theories. Nevertheless, it is identified that the intention to revisit is influenced by the theoretical components of theory of planned behaviour, viz., attitude, social support and the traveller's confidence. Confirmation, generalization and prediction may be possible with the support of theory of planned behaviour. Attitude toward behaviour, viz., the degree to which a person has positive or negative feelings on food choices, entails a consideration of the outcomes of performing the behaviour intention to revisit Rainforest World Music Festival. Subjective Norm in this research may be connected to the social support institutions like family members, peer groups etc. acting as reference group, which develop the belief about food choices, due to which the travellers will perform the behaviour. It relates to a person's perception of the reference group surrounding the behaviour, leading to a favourable or unfavourable decision to attend the event. Last but not least component in this theoretical frame is the perceived behavioural control variable self-efficacy. This refers to the individual's perception of the extent to which performance of the behaviour, visit or revisit the Rainforest World Music Festival is easy or difficult in relation to food choices (Ajzen, 1991).

CONCLUSION

The objective of this research was to identify the food choice categories connected to food choice behaviour. These categories further develop experiential food choice attitude among the travellers. Further, the research also intended to come up with a theoretical model, which explores the relationship between food choice attitude and intention revisit. The study posed one qualitative research question to identify the categories linked to food choice attitude. The study identified 14 food categories, which explains the neophobic attitude of travellers visiting the Rain Forest World Music Festival, with the support of phenomenological approach and case study methodology integrating triangulated tools of interview, observations and content analysis. These attitudinal variables can be connected to theory of planned behaviour to explain the relationship between food choice attitude and intention to revisit Rain Forest Music Festival. This part of the study turned to be first phase a mix method research design, viz., sequential exploratory study design, which end up with the identification and understanding of the food choice categories and its possible relation with traveller's intention to revisit Rain Forest Music Festival with Theory of Planned Behaviour.

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